

The pragmatics of *wh*-in situ questions in Greek

Abstract

Recently, it has been argued that a *wh*-fronting or *wh*-in situ arrangement in Greek may each map to two readings: a true interrogative one and an echo interpretation. This raises the question as to how the two readings are disambiguated. A recent account places disambiguation between PF and LF: PF assigns each construction a distinct melody, which translates to a certain interpretation at LF. This paper maintains that prosody affects interpretation, but places the relevant disambiguation in the pragmatics.

1. Introduction

Wh-elements in Greek may either front, as in [1a], or surface ‘in situ’, as in [1b].

- [1] a. Ke pja nomizis oti idhe?
 and who-ACC think-2SG that saw-3SG
 b. Ke nomizis oti idhe PJA?
 and think-2SG that saw-3SG who-ACC
 ‘And, whom do you think s/he saw?’

Typically, the *wh*-fronting configuration has been assumed to translate to an “information-seeking” question (hereafter, IQ), where the value of the variable discharged by the *wh*-element is unknown to the speaker who asks the question. This reading contrasts sharply with that of the in situ arrangement in [1b], which is usually taken to facilitate an echo interpretation (henceforth, EQ), where the speaker does not seek for information, but for confirmation of something that has already been said (e.g., Agouraki 1990; Tsimpli 1990; 1995; 1998; Carnie 2006).¹

However, more recently, it has been shown that both [1a] and [1b] are felicitous with either IQ or EQ reading, as in [2a] and [2b] below (Sinopoulou 2009; Vlachos 2010; 2012; 2014; Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou 2013).

- [2] a. Ke pja/PJA nomizis oti idhe?
 and who-ACC think-2SG that saw-3SG

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¹ Here, and throughout, we will capitalize echo occurrences for ease of comparison with non-echo ones.

- b. Ke nomizis oti idhe PJA/pja?
 and think-2SG that saw-3SG who-ACC
 ‘And, who do you think s/he saw?’

Vlachos (2014), building on Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou (2013), maintains that it is not syntax that distinguishes between the two readings in [2], but PF, which assigns distinct prosodies to each interpretation. From this perspective, disambiguation takes place in the semantics of the relevant constructions.

In the present paper, we will also maintain that prosody affects interpretation, but we will propose that the relevant disambiguation takes place in pragmatics, not in semantics.

The discussion unfolds as follows: Section 2 summarizes Vlachos’s (2014) approach, Section 3 offers a necessary background on pragmatics, Section 4 pans out the proposal of the present paper, while Section 5 concludes the discussion.

2. Disambiguating *wh*-meanings: Vlachos’s (2014) semantic account

Vlachos’s (2014) proposal builds on Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou’s (2013) empirical observations regarding the distribution, interpretation, and intonation, of *wh*-fronting and in situ IQs and EQs (who, in turn, take the lead from Vlachos 2012). So, before we embark on Vlachos’s system, it is appropriate to summarize the relevant evidence from interpretation and intonation, while we will put aside the facts from distribution.

Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou (2013) show that, unlike *wh*-fronting IQs, *wh*-in situ counterparts are infelicitous with aggressively non-D-linked phrases, such as *on earth* (e.g., Pesetsky 1987; den Dikken & Giannakidou 2002), and non-exhaustivity markers, like *for example* (e.g., Beck & Rullman 1999). *Wh*-in situ IQs become felicitous only in linguistic contexts that make available a set of alternative values, from which the relevant *wh*-element may draw. This is not the case with the fronting configurations, which are oblivious to the absence of a pre-established set of alternative values, and are felicitous in so-called “out-of-the-blue” environments. Drawing from the literature on the semantics of questions (e.g., Karttunen 1977; Groenendijk & Stokhof 1984; Heim 1994; Beck & Rullman 1999), Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou (2013) argue that *wh*-fronting IQs bear “non-exhaustive” quantification, while the quantification of the in situ counterparts is “exhaustive”. Now, in EQs, both fronting or in situ, the *wh*-element presupposes no set of alternative values, either non-exhaustively or exhaustively, but maps to a single value, which is available in the linguistic environment. From this perspective, and compared to the quantification of IQs, Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou (2013) conjecture that, irrespective of their surface position, EQs lack quantification, on the assumption that the notion “(*wh*-)quantification” entails the notion “set of values”. Borrowing a term from Tsimplici (1998), Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou (2013) dub the corresponding EQ reading individual.

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Turning to intonation, Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou (2013) document the following results of an experiment that emulates the natural production of the arrangements under consideration, in laboratory conditions ([3]–[6] corresponds to Vlachos’s 2014, 222–25, [9]–[12], respectively, excluding the relevant panels for reasons of space).

- [3] a. Ke pja nomizis oti idhe?
 and who-ACC think-2SG that saw-3SG
 ‘And, who do you think s/he saw?’
 b. L*+H L- !H%
- [4] a. Ke nomizis oti idhe pja?
 and think-2SG that saw-3SG who-ACC
 ‘And, who do you think s/he saw?’
 b. L*+H L+H* L- H*L-H%
- [5] a. PJA idhe?
 who-ACC saw-3SG
 ‘S/he saw WHO?’
 b. L* L- H%
- [6] a. Idhe PJA?
 saw-3SG who-ACC
 ‘S/he saw WHO?’
 b. L* L- L* L- H%

As in [3], the pitch accent of a *wh*-fronting IQ (cf., [3a]) is L*+H, the phrase accent is L-, and the boundary tone is a !H% (cf., [3b]; also Arvaniti 2001). The same intonation contour concentrates on the in situ *wh*-element in [4a], while the part of the utterance that precedes *pja* ‘who’ constructs an intermediate intonation phrase which maps to a typical pre-focus element, with two pitch accents, that is, L*+H L+H*, and a L- phrase accent (cf., [4b]). In short, as Roussou, Vlachos & Papazachariou (2013) point out, the same prosody that expands over the whole utterance in the case of *wh*-fronting IQs, as in [3], shrinks in a shorter surface vis-à-vis *wh*-in situ IQs (cf., [4]). A similar expanding vs. shrinking pattern is manifested in EQs, which have a clearly distinct intonation contour. More in particular, the melody of *wh*-fronting EQs is L* L- H% (cf., [5b]), which concentrates on the in situ *wh*-counterpart in [6b], while the intonation contour that precedes forms an intermediate intonation phrase, described as L* L-.

The aforementioned facts show clearly that each interpretation corresponds to a distinct prosody. Capitalizing on this observation, Vlachos (2014) suggests that PF distinguishes between IQ and EQ readings at LF, by assigning clearly distinct intonation contours. In particular, the author proposes the following PF-LF pairing (his, [21]).

- [7] a. L* +H (or H*) L- !H% (IQ) = (non-)exhaustive quantification.
 i. Spreading contour = non-exhaustive quantification.
 ii. Shrinking contour = exhaustive quantification.
 b. L* L- H% (EQ) = no quantification (individual reading).
 i. Spreading/Shrinking contour = no quantification.

In a nutshell, [7] says that the melody of IQs maps to non-exhaustive quantification, if it expands over the whole utterance, in the case of the *wh*-fronting configuration, and to exhaustive quantification, if it concentrates on the *wh*-element, as in *wh*-in situ arrangements. The EQ prosody maps to no quantification, irrespective of the relevant arrangement.

To couch the aforementioned mapping in more formal terms, Vlachos (2014) draws from Vergnaud & Zubizarreta's (2005) (henceforth, V&Z) approach to French fronting and in situ *wh*-questions, whose interpretation also varies in tandem with their corresponding prosodies. For space limitations, we will gloss over much technical details, and will demonstrate how V&Z's system works by restricting attention to Vlachos's adaptation to Greek, in the context of [8], [9], and [10] ([8] and [10] correspond to Vlachos's 2014, 234–36, [23], [26] & [27], while [9] is modelled on his [25]).

- [8] a. OR^{δ} =_{def} “inclusive/informational *or*”, “contrastive *or*” (*i,c*).
 b. OR^i =_{def} “inclusive/informational *or*”.
 c. OR^c =_{def} “contrastive *or*”.
- [9] a. non-exhaustive quantification = OR^i .
 b. exhaustive quantification = OR^c .
 c. individual reading = ΘR (no quantification).
- [10] a. Me pjon xorepses?
 with whom danced-2SG
 ‘With whom did you dance?’
 b. (You Past dance with someone) OR^i (You Past dance with someone else).
 c. Xorepses me pjon?
 danced-2SG with whom
 ‘With whom did you dance?’
 d. (You Past dance with someone) OR^c (You Past dance with someone else).
 e. ME PJON xorepses (ME PJON)?
 with whom danced-2SG with whom
 ‘WITH WHOM (did) you dance(d) (WITH WHOM)?’
 f. You Past dance with someone.

[8] defines the quantification of a *wh*-question as a disjunction between (or, among, for that matter) alternative propositions. This disjunction is formally captured with an operator OR, which may be either unspecified (superscripted with δ ; cf., [8a]) or specified. If the latter, OR is either inclusive/informational (OR^i ; cf., [8b]) or contrastive (OR^c ; cf., [8c]). [9] says that the non-exhaustive quantification maps to inclusive/informational OR^i (cf., [9a]), the exhaustive to contrastive OR^c (cf., [9b]), while the individual reading yields no quantification (ΘR ; cf., [9c]). Within these assumptions in place, Vlachos proposes the relevant LF's in [10]: the *wh*-fronting IQ in [10a] translates to the LF in [10b], the *wh*-in situ IQ in [10c] maps to the LF in [10d], while EQs, both fronting and in situ (cf., [10e], which collapses the two occurrences for simplicity), have the LF in [10f].

For Vlachos (and V&Z), the interpretation of OR above depends on the corre-

sponding prosodies, as the following mapping demonstrates (fashioned over Vlachos's 2014, 236, [28]; see also [7]).

- [11] a. $L^* +H$ (or H^*) $L- !H\%$ (IQ) = (non-)exhaustive quantification = OR^δ .
 i. Spreading contour = non-exhaustive quantification = OR^i .
 ii. Shrinking contour = exhaustive quantification = OR^c .
 b. $L^* L- H\%$ (EQ) = no quantification (individual reading) = $\emptyset R$.
 i. Spreading/Shrinking contour = no quantification = $\emptyset R$.

Building on [7] above, [11] says that the intonation contour of a *wh*-fronting IQ maps to an unspecified OR^δ , which may give rise to either non-exhaustive or exhaustive quantification (cf., [11a]). The spreading contour gives rise to OR^i (cf., [11a.i]), while the shrinking melody to OR^c (cf., [11a.ii]). EQ melodies, on the other hand, cancel the quantifier OR (cf., [11b]), irrespective of the way the relevant melody falls on each utterance (cf., [11b.ii]).

3. Disjunction and Gricean Pragmatic theory

Based on the discussion above, two main questions arise: (i) assuming that a *wh*-question is a disjunction (OR) between alternative propositions why accept an ambiguous OR account instead of a more economic implicature account; and (ii) if prosody (PF) may affect interpretation, why not hypothesize that the relevant readings are calculated in pragmatics (instead of semantics). In the remainder of this paper, building upon the theoretical findings so far, we shall attempt a pragmatic account of *wh*-in situ questions in Greek.

3.1 Disjunction

In natural languages connective OR appears to be different from disjunction in the sense that it appears ambiguous between two main readings, namely, the inclusive reading (as *p or q or both*) and the exclusive one (as *p or q but not both*). By way of illustration consider the examples:

[12] An applicant should have a degree in engineering or five years of programming experience

[13] John is a TV presenter or a physicist

In [12] an applicant is fine if she has both a degree in engineering and five years of programming experience and therefore, the inclusive reading is favored. By contrast, in [13] the exclusive reading will be preferred since *p* and *q* cannot be both true.

The question whether to interpret OR as lexically ambiguous or not is a long-standing issue in the literature. However, given the modified Occam's Razor according to which senses are not to be multiplied beyond necessity, Grice (1978) proposes an alternative to ambiguity claim. More accurately, the two senses of OR can be accounted for if we assume one basic interpretation and then derive all other read-

ings by means of pragmatic inferences. Following this, the sense of OR is considered univocal and inclusive (*p or q or both*); so the inclusive interpretation is the basic one. The exclusive reading (*p or q but not both*) is not part of the propositional content but it is derived pragmatically by a conversational implicature.

3.2 Gricean Maxims and scalar implicature

Grice builds his theory on the supposition that conversation moves along certain guidelines and assumptions. As Grice (1975, 45) states, “our talk exchanges do not normally consist of a succession of disconnected remarks [...] they are, to some degree at least, co-operative efforts”. Moreover, this co-operativeness is assumed for both the speaker and the hearer in a reciprocal manner. On these grounds, the theory of conversational implicature includes an overarching principle which Grice dubs as the co-operative principle. The co-operative principle of communication is defined in Grice (1975, 45) along the following lines:

The co-operative principle:

Make your conversational contribution such as is required at the stage at which it occurs, by the accepted purpose or direction of the talk exchange in which you are engaged (Grice 1989, 26).

The co-operative principle is further subdivided into four conversational maxims and eight sub-maxims. According to Grice, the maxims along with the co-operative principle regulate efficient language use in communication:

The Gricean maxims of conversation:

Quality: Try to make your contribution on that is true.

- (i) Do not say what you believe to be false
- (ii) Do not say that for which you lack adequate evidence

Quantity:

- (i) Make your contribution as informative as is required (for the current purposes of the exchange).
- (ii) Do not make your contribution more informative than is required.

Relation: Be relevant.

Manner: Be perspicuous.

- (i) Avoid obscurity of expression.
- (ii) Avoid ambiguity.
- (iii) Be brief (avoid unnecessary prolixity).
- (iv) Be orderly.

(Grice 1989, 26–27)

The part of the Gricean maxims of conversation that is most relevant for our discussion is quantity implicatures. Quantity implicatures are triggered by the exploitation of the Gricean maxim of quantity and they are negative inferences in the sense that they refer to something that could have been said but was not said. Consider the example:

[14] A: Did Einstein proposed General Relativity and the Exclusion Principle?

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- B: Well, Einstein proposed General Relativity
Implicature: Einstein did not propose the Exclusion Principle

In [14] B implies that the answer to A's question is not both. In this way she communicates the negation of A's statement implicitly.

A special case of quantity implicatures is *scalar implicature*. Particular linguistic expressions form entailment scales that are ordered in terms of the informational strength of utterances that contain them. A classic scale of this kind is quantifiers <all, some>. In such a scale the semantic entailment has one direction making sure that the item to the left of the scale is informationally stronger than the item to the right (for more see Horn 1989; Levinson 2000, among others).

- [15] Some of Einstein's predictions are wrong
Implicature: not all of Einstein's predictions are wrong

Given the first maxim of quantity, in the above example, the use of an utterance containing the informationally weaker term 'some' where an alternative proposition containing the informationally stronger term 'all' could have used will trigger a quantity implicature communicating that the stronger claim does not hold. The implicated meaning is based on the negative nature of the inference since if the speaker could have made the stronger claim, she would have done so.

Concerning our analysis, connective 'or' is a typical case of a scalar item. In particular, 'or' forms an informativeness scale with 'and'. 'And' is semantically stronger and stands for logical conjunction (\wedge) while 'or' is semantically weaker and stands for logical disjunction (\vee). Following the same rationale as in [15] to say *p or q*, will implicate $\neg(p \text{ and } q)$ i.e. the use of the informationally weaker term where the informationally stronger could have used will conversationally implicate that the proposition including the stronger one does not hold. As mentioned already, the apparent ambiguity of connective 'or' between the inclusive and the exclusive readings can be resolved by deriving the latter pragmatically by a conversational implicature. What is actually proposed (see Levinson 1983 among others) is that the exclusive reading is a combination of the logical disjunction and the scalar implicature, namely, $p \vee q$ and $\neg(p \wedge q)$ gives *p or q* but not both.

One last crucial issue relevant to scalar implicatures is that they do not arise in contexts where the implicature would not contribute to making the utterance more informative (Katsos & Breheny 2010). Consider the following examples:

- [16] A: Who proposed the Exclusion Principle?
B: It was Pauli or Heisenberg
- [17] A: What reading would you suggest for the assignment?
B: Study Pauli or Heisenberg and you will be fine.

Example [16] introduces an upper-bound context in the sense that interlocutors are interested in the strongest information possible and therefore the inclusive reading (*p or q* or *both*) is not enough. By contrast, the implicated exclusive reading (*p or q*

but not both) increases the amount of contextually relevant information communicated by the speaker. The exclusive interpretation of the connective ‘or’ is an upper-bounded interpretation. Consider now the example in [17]. Here, the basic interpretation of the scalar item (i.e. the inclusive one) is sufficient for addressing the discourse goal and consequently, the scalar implicature will not be triggered. Contexts where computing the scalar implicature would be redundant are named lower-bound contexts and the inclusive interpretation of the connective ‘or’ is a lower-bounded interpretation.

Against this background, in the remainder of this paper we shall explore the possibility that the prosody ‘sees’ the pragmatics of the iterative disjunction between alternative propositions in *wh*-in situ questions in Greek.

4. Disambiguating *wh*-meanings: A pragmatic account

Assuming (i) the analysis of V&Z according to which a *wh*-question translates to a(n) (iterative) disjunction between alternative propositions and (ii) the implicature account on disjunction, we will argue that the interpretation of *wh*-in situ questions in Greek can be placed in the division of labour between intonation and pragmatics. A way forward is to suggest that the semantics of IQs (LF reading) is always inclusive (*p or q or even both*) and remains so unless it becomes exclusive (*p or q but not both*) by way of a scalar implicature.

By using the relevant intonation when uttering the question the speaker reveals her communicative intentions in the following way. A spreading melody will convey that anything goes as an answer and therefore, the semantic meaning of *or* (*p or q or even both*) is relevant. On the contrary, by opting for a shrinking melody and forming an in situ question the speaker communicates that the *wh*-element selects a member from a set of alternatives in the context so the semantic meaning of *or* is not informative enough. By assuming co-operative communication, a scalar implicature will be triggered inducing an upper-bounding interpretation (*p or q but not both*). Let us illustrate with some examples:

- [18] a. Pjios diatipose ti theoria tis genikis sxetikotitas?
 who-NOM proposed-3SG the theory of General Relativity
 ‘Who proposed General Relativity?’
 b. spreading pattern L*+H (or H*) L-!H%

Given that a *wh*-question is captured as a(n) (iterative) disjunction between alternative propositions the LF of [18] can be glossed as follows:

- [19] LF: (the theory was introduced by X) ORi (the theory was introduced by Y)

As it is claimed, the LF reading of IQs is always inclusive and remains so unless the speaker intends an exclusive (exhaustive quantification) reading by using a shrinking melody pattern. In [18] the spreading *wh*-fronting IQ melody will not trigger the SI because in this context the LF reading of OR (i.e. inclusive) is more informative.

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The speaker by using a spreading melody (which is preferred in *wh*-fronting IQs) intends to communicate that a non-exhaustive quantification reading is preferred i.e. any answer is possible. By contrast, consider the scenario in which Lucy and Sandra want to go for a city break on the weekend but they haven't any ideas on where to go. Lucy said that she went to a travel agency and they recommended to her Rome, London and Madrid. Then Sandra asks [20]:

- [20] a. Ke tha pame pou?
 and will go-3PL where
 'And, where are we going?'
 b. shrinking pattern H* L- H%

Again, the LF of the question above contains an inclusive disjunction as in [21]. Nevertheless, what is actually communicated is the proposition in [22].

[21] LF: (we will go at X) ORⁱ (we will go at Y)

[22] LF: (we will go at X) OR^c (we will go at Y)

Here, the shrinking melody (which is preferred with *wh*-in situ IQs) will trigger the SI because this implicature-driven interpretation of OR is more informative bearing context in mind. The speaker by using a shrinking melody intends to communicate that the *wh*-element selects a member from a set of alternatives in the context and hence an exhaustive quantification reading is preferred.

The proposed implicature account apart from explaining how the speaker reveals her communicative intentions by opting for the relevant intonation when uttering the question, it also predicts that the role of context is critical in the interpretation of *wh*-IQs. It can be argued that the absence of a potential answer in the context introduces a lower-bound context whereas the presence of a set of possible answers in the micro-discourse introduces an upper-bound context. As mentioned earlier in the discussion, SIs are generally triggered in upper-bound contexts since they convey the logically strongest information possible by increasing the amount of contextually relevant information communicated by the speaker. By contrast, in lower-bound contexts the semantic meaning is informative enough and hence a SI reading is not necessary. Therefore, it is explained why *wh*-fronting IQs are felicitous in aggressively non-D-linked (hence lower-bound) contexts while in situ questions are preferred in contexts where there are potential answers already established in the discourse.

5. Conclusions

Revisiting an earlier approach to the disambiguation of Greek *wh*-fronting and in situ information-seeking (IQ) and echo (EQ) questions, this paper claimed that prosody affects interpretation, but crucially, it interfaces with the pragmatics, and not semantics. The key proposal is that the semantics of IQs is always inclusive (*p or q or*

even both) and remains so unless it becomes exclusive (*p or q but not both*) by way of a scalar implicature in the spirit of Grice's first maxim of quantity. Thus intonation may affect pragmatics (pace voices to the opposite direction, e.g., Fiengo 2007).

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